

Quantitative Proteomics Identifies the Membrane-Associated Peroxidase GPx8 as a Cellular Substrate of the Hepatitis C Virus NS3-4A Protease

Kenichi Morikawa^{1#*}, Jérôme Gouttenoire^{1*}, Céline Hernandez^{2,3}, Viet Loan Dao Thi¹,
Huong T. L. Tran¹, Christian M. Lange^{1¶}, Michael T. Dill⁴, Markus H. Heim⁴, Olivier Donzé⁵,
François Penin⁶, Manfred Quadroni², and Darius Moradpour^{1*}

¹Division of Gastroenterology and Hepatology, Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois,
²Protein Analysis Facility and ³Vital-IT Group, Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, University of
Lausanne, Switzerland; ⁴Division of Gastroenterology and Hepatology, University Hospital
Basel, Switzerland; ⁵ Adipogen SA, CH-1066 Epalinges, Switzerland; and ⁶Institut de
Biologie et Chimie des Protéines, Bases Moléculaires et Structurales des
Systèmes Infectieux, UMR 5086, CNRS, University of Lyon, France

Running title: Targeting of GPx8 by HCV NS3-4A

FOOTNOTE PAGE

Contact Information

*Corresponding author. Division of Gastroenterology and Hepatology, Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois, Rue du Bugnon 44, CH-1011 Lausanne, Switzerland; Phone +41 21 314 47 14, Fax +41 21 314 47 18, E-mail: Darius.Moradpour@chuv.ch

#Current affiliation: Division of Gastroenterology and Hepatology, Showa University School of Medicine, Tokyo, Japan

†Current affiliation: Department of Medicine I, University Hospital Frankfurt a.M., Germany.

*These authors contributed equally to this work.

List of Abbreviations

DDB1, UV-damaged DNA-binding protein 1; ER, endoplasmic reticulum; Ero1 α , ER oxidoreductin-1 α ; GFP, green fluorescent protein; GPx8, glutathione peroxidase 8; GST, glutathione S-transferase; HCV, hepatitis C virus; HCVcc, cell culture-derived HCV; HCVpp, HCV pseudoparticle; IFN- α , interferon- α ; mAb, monoclonal antibody; LC-MS/MS, liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry; mAb, monoclonal antibody; MAVS, mitochondrial antiviral signaling protein; MS, mass spectrometry; NS3-4A, nonstructural protein 3-4A; PDI, protein disulfide isomerase; POPC, 1-palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-3-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine; SDS, sodium dodecyl sulfate; SDS-PAGE, sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis; SILAC, stable isotopic labeling using amino acids in cell culture; TC-PTP, T-cell protein tyrosine phosphatase; TCID₅₀, 50% tissue culture infective dose ; TRIF, TIR domain-containing adapter molecule 1.

Financial Support

This work was supported by grants 3100A0-122447 and 31003A-138484 from the Swiss National Science Foundation.

ABSTRACT

The hepatitis C virus (HCV) NS3-4A protease is not only an essential component of the viral replication complex and a prime target for antiviral intervention but also a key player in the persistence and pathogenesis of HCV. It cleaves and thereby inactivates two crucial adaptor proteins in viral RNA sensing and innate immunity, MAVS and TRIF, a phosphatase involved in growth factor signaling, TC-PTP, and the E3 ubiquitin ligase component DDB1. Here, we explored quantitative proteomics to identify novel cellular substrates of the NS3-4A protease. Cell lines inducibly expressing the NS3-4A protease were analyzed by stable isotopic labeling using amino acids in cell culture (SILAC) coupled with protein separation and mass spectrometry. This approach identified the membrane-associated peroxidase GPx8 as a *bona fide* cellular substrate of the HCV NS3-4A protease. Cleavage by NS3-4A occurs at Cys 11, removing the cytosolic tip of GPx8, and was observed in different experimental systems as well as in liver biopsies from patients with chronic hepatitis C. Overexpression and RNA silencing studies revealed that GPx8 is involved in viral particle production but not in HCV entry or RNA replication. In conclusion, we provide proof-of-concept for the use of quantitative proteomics to identify cellular substrates of a viral protease and describe GPx8 as a novel proviral host factor targeted by the HCV NS3-4A protease.

Keywords: glutathione peroxidase 8 | HCV | mass spectrometry | NS3-4A | SILAC

INTRODUCTION

Hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection is a leading cause of chronic hepatitis, liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma worldwide, with a disease burden predicted to increase further for the next 10 years.¹ HCV NS3-4A is a multifunctional complex composed of nonstructural protein 3 (NS3) and its cofactor NS4A. It harbors serine protease as well as NTPase/RNA helicase activities and is essential for viral polyprotein processing, RNA replication, and assembly.^{2,3} Given its central role in the viral life cycle, NS3-4A has been actively pursued as antiviral target, and a first generation of NS3-4A protease inhibitors has been approved for the treatment of chronic hepatitis C (ref. 4 and references therein).

The NS3-4A protease has been found to also target selected cellular proteins. Indeed, it cleaves and thereby inactivates mitochondrial antiviral signaling protein (MAVS) as well as TIR domain-containing adaptor molecule 1 (TRIF⁶), two key adaptor molecules in the RIG-I and TLR3 viral RNA-sensing pathways, respectively (see ref. 3 for review and abbreviations). In addition, NS3-4A has been reported to cleave T-cell protein tyrosine phosphatase (TC-PTP), thereby modulating growth factor signaling,⁷ UV-damaged DNA-binding protein 1 (DDB1), a core component of the CUL4-based E3 ubiquitin ligase complex.⁸ Hence, NS3-4A is not only an essential component of the viral replication complex and a prime target for antiviral intervention but also a key player in the persistence and pathogenesis of HCV.

Here, we aimed to identify novel cellular substrates of the HCV NS3-4A protease. Searching for such cellular targets in an unbiased fashion represents a challenge. Bioinformatic approaches are likely to fail, as a vast number of cellular proteins display the NS3-4A consensus cleavage sequence D/E-X-X-X-X-C/T | S/A-X-X-X (P6-P1 | P1'-P4'). Moreover, the cellular substrates identified so far have less canonical cleavage sites (reviewed in ref. 3). In addition, our previous work has demonstrated that the processing and structural organization of NS3-4A are intrinsically linked to intracellular membranes and that proper positioning of the protease active site with respect to the membrane may represent a determinant of substrate selectivity.⁹

Based on these premises, we explored large-scale proteomics technologies to identify novel cellular substrates of the HCV NS3-4A protease. An approach was needed that permits accurate relative protein quantitation and at the same time could be coupled to a separation technique able to discriminate full-length proteins from their cleavage products. Hence, we employed stable isotopic labeling using amino acids in cell culture (SILAC) which had demonstrated high sensitivity, broad proteome coverage and accuracy.¹⁰ SILAC was coupled with molecular weight-based protein separation, mass spectrometry (MS), and a dedicated

data analysis approach to detect and quantify comprehensively the species as well as the migration patterns of proteins from cells expressing or not the NS3-4A protease.

This quantitative proteomics approach followed by experimental validation identified the membrane-associated peroxidase GPx8 as a cellular substrate of the NS3-4A protease. GPx8 cleavage by NS3-4A occurs at Cys 11, removing the cytosolic tip of GPx8, and was observed in different experimental systems as well as in liver biopsies from patients with chronic hepatitis C. Furthermore, overexpression and RNA silencing studies revealed that GPx8 is involved in viral particle production but not in HCV entry or RNA replication. Thus, we provide a proof-of-concept for the use of advanced proteomics for the identification of cellular substrates of a viral protease and describe GPx8 as a novel proviral host factor targeted by the HCV NS3-4A protease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents. Monoclonal antibody (mAb) Adri-1 and mAb 1B6 against MAVS and HCV NS3, respectively, were from Adipogen (Epalinges, Switzerland). MAb ANTI-FLAG[®] M2 and mAb AC-15 against β -actin were from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO). MAbs JS-81 and M-L13 against CD81 and CD9, respectively, were from BD Biosciences (Franklin Lakes, NJ). Mab C7-50 against HCV core was from Abcam (Cambridge, United Kingdom).

The U-2 OS human osteosarcoma-derived cell lines UNS3-4A-24 and UHCVcon-57.3, allowing tetracycline-regulated expression of the NS3-4A complex derived from the prototype HCV H77 (genotype 1a) clone¹¹ and of the entire polyprotein derived from the HCV H77 consensus clone,¹² respectively, have been described.^{13,14} Huh-7.5 cells were kindly provided by Charles M. Rice (The Rockefeller University, New York, NY).¹⁵

SILAC, protein separation and MS. UNS3-4A-24 cells were heavy isotope labeled by culture in modified RPMI 1640 medium in which ¹³C₆-L-lysine and ¹³C₆¹⁵N₄-L-arginine (Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Andover, MA) were present at 100 mg/l, whereas proline was supplemented at 180 mg/l. All other amino acids were present at standard concentrations. A parallel culture designated "light" was maintained in the same medium containing standard unlabeled amino acids. Dialyzed fetal bovine serum at a concentration of 10%, 4 mM L-glutamine and 1 μ g/ml tetracycline were added to all media.

Cell lines were cultured for 6 passages in the above medium to achieve complete labeling (heavy labeling > 98% and arginine-to-proline conversion < 5%). NS3-4A protease expression was induced by tetracycline withdrawal during 48 h, with or without stimulation with interferon- α (IFN- α) 1000 IU/ml (Roche, Basel, Switzerland) for 24 h before harvest. Cell extracts were mixed at a quantitative ratio of 1:1, and a total of 20 μ g of protein was separated by gradient sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE). After Coomassie staining, each lane was cut into either 56 (first screen) or 64 slices (second screen), followed by in-gel digestion with trypsin, as described.¹⁶ The supernatants from each digestion reaction were concentrated and analyzed on a hybrid linear trap LTQ-Orbitrap Velos mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher, Bremen, Germany) interfaced *via* a nanospray source to a Dionex RSLC 3000 nanoHPLC system (Dionex, Sunnyvale, CA) (see Supplementary Materials and Methods for details).

MS data analysis. MS data were analyzed and quantified with standard parameters using MaxQuant version 1.0.13.13 (ref. 17) and the IPI database (human subset) version 3.52 (see Supplementary Material and Methods for details). Results from MaxQuant were filtered and processed further with custom-built software tools. The first was a Perl script (Suppl. File 1) to identify proteins present in at least two distinct gel slices with different SILAC ratios, as

described in the Results section. Next, the evidence counts and normalized SILAC ratios for these selected proteins were visualized as a function of the gel slice with an R script (Suppl. File 2 and Legend to Suppl. Fig. 1).

Plasmids and recombinant viruses. As described in more detail in the Supplementary Materials and Methods, a GPx8 cDNA was cloned from U-2 OS cells and FLAG-tagged expression constructs were prepared in pcDNA3.1(+) (Invitrogen, La Jolla, CA). The cDNA encoding GPx8 amino acids 38-209 was cloned into pGEX-6P-1 (GE Healthcare, Buckinghamshire, UK) for production of a glutathione S-transferase (GST) fusion protein. The GPx8 cDNA was cloned into pLPCX (Clontech, Mountain View, CA) for production of a recombinant retrovirus.

Plasmid pCMVNS3-4A and its catalytically inactive counterpart pCMVNS3_{S139A}-4A, harboring a Ser-to-Ala mutation in NS3 amino acid position 139, have been described.^{9,13} pFKi389LucNS3-3'_dg_JFH¹⁸ and pFK-JFH1J6C-846_dg¹⁹ were kindly provided by Ralf Bartenschlager (University of Heidelberg, Germany).

***In vitro* transcription, electroporation, transient replication and infection assays.** *In vitro* transcription of subgenomic replicon and full-length HCV RNA as well as electroporation were performed as described (ref. 20 and references therein). RNA replication assay using a JFH1 subgenomic replicon harboring the firefly luciferase was performed as described previously.^{18,21} Jc1 cell culture-derived HCV (HCVcc) was produced as described.¹⁹ The 50% tissue culture infective dose (TCID₅₀) was determined as described.²²

Retroviral transduction. Recombinant retroviral particles were prepared in 293T cells by cotransfection of pLPCXGPx8 or pLPCX-GFP (kindly provided by Angela Ciuffi, University of Lausanne, Switzerland) and packaging constructs pMLV-NB and pMD.G (kindly provided by Didier Trono, Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Switzerland), as described previously.²³

RNA silencing. GPx8 siRNAs #1 (s54629) and #2 (s54630) were purchased from Ambion (Life Technologies, Carlsbad, CA). A non-targeted siRNA served as control (Silencer Select Negative Control #1, Ambion). RNAiMAX was used for siRNA transfection (Invitrogen).

HCV pseudoparticle production and infection assays. HCV pseudoparticles (HCVpp) were produced as described previously.²⁴

Recombinant protein expression and antibody production. Polyclonal antibody IN103 against GPx8 was produced by immunization of a rabbit with GPx8[38-209] expressed as GST fusion protein in *E. coli*. This antibody is now available from Adipogen (AG-25B-0028).

Liver biopsies. Liver biopsy specimens from patients with chronic hepatitis C and controls were obtained in the context of routine diagnostic workup and snap frozen for research

purposes if there was sufficient material for histopathological examination and the patient's written informed consent had been provided in accordance with the Ethics Committee of Basel.

Molecular modeling. The following algorithms were combined for the prediction of the GPx8 transmembrane segment: PHDhtm (<http://www.predictprotein.org/>), TMHMM (<http://www.cbs.dtu.dk/services/TMHMM>), DAS (<http://www.sbc.su.se/miklos/DAS/>), TopPred2 (http://mobyli.pasteur.fr/cgi-bin/MobyliPortal/portal.py?form_toppred), Tmpred (http://www.ch.embnet.org/software/TMPRED_form.html), HMMTOP (<http://www.enzim.hu/hmmtop/>), and SOSUI (<http://bp.nuap.nagoya-u.ac.jp/sosui/>). Sequences similar to that of the GPx8 N-terminal amino acid segment 1-38 were searched for in the Protein Data Bank by using the SSEARCH program in the IBCP website facilities (<http://npsa-pbil.ibcp.fr/>)²⁵ and structural models were constructed using Swiss PDB-viewer (<http://www.expasy.org/spdbv/>).²⁶

RESULTS

Identification of GPx8 as novel cellular substrate of the HCV NS3-4A protease. The UNS3-4A-24 cell line, allowing the tightly regulated expression of a functional HCV NS3-4A protease, was subjected to SILAC, followed by protein separation and MS, as illustrated in Figure 1. Two screens were performed, a first one comparing cells expressing or not the NS3-4A complex and a second one with the additional stimulation with IFN- α . Immunoblots of the cell lysates that were subjected to SDS-PAGE and MS demonstrate the tightly regulated expression of NS3-4A, cleavage of MAVS as a true cellular substrate of the NS3-4A protease, and upregulation of Stat1 as a control for the IFN- α stimulation (Suppl. Fig. 2).

FIG. 1. Quantitative proteomics using stable isotopic labeling with amino acids in cell culture (SILAC). Two populations of UNS3-4A-24 cells were fully labeled with either normal (light) or heavy isotopes. Expression of the HCV NS3-4A protease was induced in one of the two cultures by tetracycline withdrawal (- tet). After lysis and protein quantitation, the two samples were mixed at a 1:1 ratio, followed by gradient sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) and cutting of the gel into multiple slices. Each gel slice was then submitted to trypsin digestion and liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). This results in identification and relative quantitation of proteins in each slice. The profiles along the gel are then reconstructed for each protein together with their abundance and heavy-over-light (H/L) ratios. Proteins with lower apparent molecular weight bands induced in protease-expressing samples were considered as candidate NS3-4A protease substrates. m/z, mass-to-charge ratio.

The SILAC workflow allowed the identification and relative quantification of up to 100 protein species per gel slice. Peptides from a total of 3642 and 5053 proteins were identified in the

first and the second screen, respectively, demonstrating the high sensitivity and broad proteome coverage of SILAC-MS. To identify protein modifications induced by NS3-4A, we explored these datasets in detail by examining the protein quantification data obtained in each gel slice separately and comparing the values for each protein across all gel slices. Indeed, the presence of the same protein in two distinct SDS-PAGE slices with opposite quantitative ratios indicates an NS3-4A-dependent shift in gel mobility, hence, possible substrates and products of the NS3-4A protease. As an important aid to interpretation and filtering of candidates we developed software tools in the Perl and R programming languages to visualize the complex patterns of bands and SILAC ratios observed (Suppl. Files 1 and 2).

The following criteria were applied to select for candidate substrates of the NS3-4A protease: (i) the protein had to be represented by at least 2 peptides per SDS-PAGE slice and (ii) the protein had to be more abundant in a lower molecular weight slice in the sample derived from cells expressing NS3-4A. Based on these criteria, GPx8 was identified as top hit in both screens and further investigated in this study.

In the first screen (in which heavy isotope-labeled cells were cultured in the presence of tetracycline, i.e. did not express the NS3-4A protease), GPx8 was detected in the absence of NS3-4A only in SDS-PAGE slice # 44 (5 peptides, H/L ratio = 9.15), harboring proteins of ~24 kDa and hence the full-length form of GPx8. In cells cultured in the absence of tetracycline (i.e. expressing NS3-4A), GPx8 was detected also in slices # 45 (4 peptides, H/L ratio = 0.03), harboring proteins of ~22 kDa. In the second screen (in which heavy isotope-labeled cells were cultured in the absence of tetracycline, i.e. expressed the NS3-4A protease), the two forms of GPx8 were identified in slices # 42 (11 peptides, H/L ratio = 0.09) vs. 43 and 44 (6 and 2 peptides with H/L ratios of 23.21 and 10.99, respectively).

The membrane-associated peroxidase GPx8 is a 209-amino acid, 24-kDa protein with an N-terminal cytosolic tip, a predicted transmembrane segment, and a catalytic domain located in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) lumen (Fig. 2A).²⁷ To experimentally validate GPx8 as candidate NS3-4A substrate, a GPx8 cDNA was cloned from U-2 OS cells, and N- or C-terminally FLAG-tagged versions of GPx8 were coexpressed with NS3-4A or a catalytically inactive control. Of note, the sequence of the GPx8 cDNA cloned in this study was identical to the one deposited in GenBank (accession number AAH29424). As shown in Figure 2B (left), GPx8 is cleaved by NS3-4A but not by the catalytically inactive control. Based on the migration pattern, cleavage was expected to occur within ~2 kDa from the N terminus of the protein. Indeed, the N-terminally tagged construct was no longer detected after coexpression with functional NS3-4A (data not shown), whereas a second, slightly faster migrating band was found after coexpression of the C-terminally tagged construct with NS3-4A but not the catalytically inactive control (Fig. 2B). As *trans*-cleavage by NS3-4A occurs after Cys residues,

we replaced the most likely target residue in GPx8 position 11 by Ala (C11A). As shown in Figure 2B (middle), this construct was no longer cleaved by NS3-4A. Finally, an N-terminally truncated GPx8 construct, in which the first 11 amino acid residues were deleted (S12), comigrated with the cleaved product derived from full-length GPx8 (Fig. 2B, right). Taken together, these results demonstrate that GPx8 is a *bona fide* substrate of the HCV NS3-4A protease and that cleavage occurs at Cys 11.

A

```

.....10.....20.....30.....40.....50
MEPLAAYPLKCSGPRARVFAVLLSIVLCTVTLFLLQLKFLKPKINSFYAF
.....60.....70.....80.....90.....100
EVKDAKGRTVSLEKYKGVSLVNVVASKQLTDRNYLGLKELHKEFGPSH
.....110.....120.....130.....140.....150
FSVLAFFPCNQFGESEPRPSKEVESFARKNYGVTFPIFHKIKILGSEGEPA
.....160.....170.....180.....190.....200
FRFLVDSSKKEPRWNFWKYLVNPEGYVVKFWRPEEPIEVIRPDIAALVRQ
.....
VIKKKEDL

```

B

FIG. 2. GPx8 is a cellular substrate of the HCV NS3-4A protease. (A) Amino acid sequence of human GPx8 (GenBank accession number AAH29424). The NS3-4A cleavage site and the predicted transmembrane segment are highlighted by an arrowhead and a box, respectively. The catalytically active site is also indicated by a white arrowhead. **(B)** U-2 OS cells were cotransfected with pCMVGPx8-FLAG, pCMVGPx8_{C11A}-FLAG or pCMVGPx8_{S12}-FLAG and pcDNA3.1(+), pCMVNS3-4A or pCMVNS3_{S139A}-4A, as indicated. Cell lysates were separated by 15% SDS-PAGE, followed by immunoblot using mAb ANTI-FLAG[®] M2.

Arrowheads denote the position of full-length (FL) and cleaved (Cl.) GPx8. Molecular weight standards are indicated on the left. **(C)** Molecular models of NS3-4A and GPx8. The model of membrane-associated NS3-4A has been described.⁹ The NS3 serine protease domain is cyan, with side chain atoms of the catalytic triad (His 57, Asp 81 and Ser 139) highlighted as purple spheres. The NS3 helicase domain is grey and the N-terminal transmembrane (amino acids 1-20) and central (amino acids 21-32) segments of NS4A are orange and light orange, respectively. Homology models of the GPx8 cytosolic tip and transmembrane segment are green while the crystal structure of the ER luminal domain is light green (PDB entry 3KIJ; ref. 27). Side chain atoms of Cys 11, representing the site of NS3-4A protease-mediated cleavage, are represented as red spheres. The membrane is represented as a simulated model of a 1-palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (POPC) bilayer (<http://moose.bio.ucalgary.ca>). Polar heads and hydrophobic tails of phospholipids (stick structures) are light yellow and gray, respectively. The figure was generated on the basis of the structure coordinates by using the Visual Molecular Dynamics program³⁴ and rendered with the POV-Ray software package.

To determine whether NS3-4A indeed interacts with GPx8, we performed co-immunoprecipitation assay and immune-fluorescent microscopic analysis (data not shown). In these experiments, NS3-4A did not interact with GPx8, suggesting that NS3-4A interacts with GPx8 temporally for a very short time.

While the crystal structure of the ER luminal domain of human GPx8 has been solved (GPx8[38-209]; PDB entry 3KIJ; ref. 27), no structure is available for the N-terminal cytosolic tip and the predicted transmembrane segment of GPx8. However, GPx8 segment 1-17 exhibits 47% identity and 71% similarity with segment 155-171 of filamin A immunoglobulin-like repeat 10 (PDB entry 3RGH; ref. 28) (Suppl. Fig. 3). Moreover, a transmembrane α -helix was predicted by all tested methods for GPx8 segment 18-37, which exhibited 26% identity and 89% similarity to the transmembrane α -helix 20-41 of FX1D protein of the sodium-potassium ATPase (PDB entry 2ZXE, chain G; ref. 29) (Suppl. Fig. 3). These observations allowed us to construct a three-dimensional homology model for the N-terminal region 1-37 of GPx8, which was connected to the luminal domain and putatively positioned in a 1-palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-3-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (POPC) bilayer, as shown in Figure 2C. This positioning was based on the assumption that the basic Lys residues at both helix ends interact with the negatively charged polar heads of phospholipids. As expected, this model shows that the α -helix has the right size to form a classical transmembrane segment. In addition, the position of GPx8 Cys 11 fits very well with the topology of the NS3-4A protease active site in the model of membrane-associated, *trans*-cleavage competent NS3-4A proposed by Brass *et al.*⁹

Endogenous GPx8 is cleaved in models of HCV infection and in liver biopsies from patients with chronic hepatitis C. To investigate whether endogenous GPx8 is cleaved by HCV NS3-4A we prepared a polyclonal antibody against an *E. coli*-expressed GST fusion protein comprising the ER luminal domain of GPx8 (GPx8[38-209]). As shown in Figure 3A, cleavage of endogenous GPx8 was observed in UNS3-4A-24 and UHCVcon-57.3 cells

cultured in the absence of tetracycline, i.e., expressing the NS3-4A complex alone or in the context of the entire HCV polyprotein, respectively. As endogenous GPx8 expression was lower in Huh-7.5 cells as compared to U-2 OS cells and cleavage by the NS3-4A protease detectable but more difficult to illustrate (data not shown), we generated by retroviral transduction a Huh-7.5 cell line stably overexpressing GPx8, designated Huh-7.5-GPx8. As shown in the right panel of Figure 3A, cleavage of GPx8 was observed in Huh-7.5-GPx8 cells upon transfection of a subgenomic HCV replicon or infection with HCVcc. Finally, cleavage of GPx8 was also observed in liver biopsies from patients with chronic hepatitis C, whereas only the full-length form of GPx8 was found in controls (Fig. 3B). Taken together, these data demonstrate that GPx8 is cleaved not only in heterologous overexpression systems but also in models of HCV infection as well as in the liver of patients with chronic hepatitis C.

FIG. 3. Cleavage of GPx8 in models of HCV infection and in liver biopsies from patients with chronic hepatitis C. (A) UNS3-4A-24 and UHCVcon-57.3 cells, inducibly expressing the NS3-4A complex alone or in the context of the entire HCV polyprotein, respectively, were cultured for 48 h in the presence or absence of tetracycline, followed by 15% SDS-PAGE and immunoblot using polyclonal antibody IN103 against GPx8. Arrowheads denote the position of full-length (FL) and cleaved (Cl.) GPx8. Similarly, Huh-7.5 cells stably overexpressing GPx8 (Huh-7.5-GPx8) were electroporated with a subgenomic replicon (sg2a, JFH1 strain) or infected with HCVcc (Jc1). Molecular weight standards are indicated on the left. **(B)** Lysates from liver biopsies of patients with chronic hepatitis C (CHC; lanes 3-5; B392, B402 and B419) as well as controls (lanes 6-7; B451 from a patient with alcoholic liver disease, B457 from a patient with chronic hepatitis B) were separated by 15% SDS-PAGE, followed by immunoblot using polyclonal antibody IN103 against GPx8. A total of 25 μ g protein per lane was loaded for the lysates from UNS3-4A-24 cells cultured in the presence or absence of tetracycline (tet) while 100 μ g protein per lane was loaded for the liver biopsy specimens. A

selection from a larger panel of liver biopsies including 8 samples from patients with CHC (of which GPx8 cleavage was detected in 3) and 6 controls (of which GPx8 cleavage was detected in none) is shown. Arrowheads denote the position of full-length (FL) and cleaved (Cl.) GPx8.

GPx8 facilitates HCV particle production. Overexpression and siRNA-mediated silencing were employed to probe for a role of GPx8 in the HCV life cycle. The HCVcc system allows investigation of the entire life cycle. Huh-7.5 cells were transduced with retroviruses expressing GPx8 or the green fluorescent protein (GFP) as a control, followed by infection with Jc1 HCVcc. Under these conditions, 90-100% of the cells overexpressed GPx8 or GFP (data not shown). As shown in Figure 4A, cells overexpressing GPx8 produced more infectious virus as compared to cells expressing GFP. In two independent experiments performed in triplicate each, TCID₅₀ yields were 1.8±0.7-fold higher upon GPx8 overexpression. Analogous results were obtained in Huh-7.5-GPx8 as compared to parental Huh-7.5 cells (2.3±0.3-fold increase in TCID₅₀ yields, n = 6; data not shown), confirming that overexpression of GPx8 reproducibly enhances infectious HCV particle production.

FIG. 4. GPx8 facilitates HCV particle production. (A) Huh-7.5 cells were transiently transduced with retroviruses (multiplicity of infection [MOI] = 10) expressing either GPx8 or green fluorescent protein (GFP), followed 2 d later by Jc1 HCVcc infection (MOI = 0.5). Extra- and intracellular infectivity were determined 3 d post-HCVcc infection by TCID₅₀ titration. Total infectivity represents the sum of extra- and intracellular infectivity. (B) Huh-7.5 cells were transfected with GPx8 siRNAs (GPx8#1, GPx8#2) or non-targeted control siRNA (nt), followed 48 h later by Jc1 HCVcc infection (MOI = 0.5). TCID₅₀ yields were determined as described in panel A as well as the Material and Methods section. (C) Huh-7.5 cells overexpressing GPx8 or GFP following retroviral transduction (see panel A) were assayed for HCV RNA replication using a JFH1 subgenomic replicon harboring a firefly luciferase reporter gene, as described in the Materials and Methods section. Luciferase activity was measured at 4, 15, 24 and 48 h post-electroporation, and relative light units (RLU) were normalized to the corresponding 4-h value. (D) Huh-7.5 cells transfected with siRNAs as described in panel B as well as the Materials and Methods section were electroporated 72 h later with subgenomic HCV replicon RNA and luciferase assay performed at 4, 15, 24 and 48 h post-electroporation. Results were normalized to the corresponding 4-h value. (E) To assess HCV entry, Huh-7.5 cells as well as Huh-7.5-GPx8 cells were transfected with siRNAs (see panel B) 24 h prior to inoculation with HCVpp. Luciferase activity was measured 72 h later. As controls for specificity, Huh-7.5 cells

were incubated 1 h prior to HCVpp infection either with monoclonal antibody (mAb) JS-81, blocking the HCV entry factor CD81, or mAb M-L13 against CD9 as a nonrelevant control.

Both GPx8 siRNAs, #1 and #2 efficiently and specifically silenced GPx8 expression (Suppl. Fig. 4). Huh-7.5 cells were transfected with GPx8 siRNAs #1 or #2 or a non-targeting control, followed by infection with Jc1 HCVcc. As shown in Figure 4B, cells produced less infectious virus following GPx8 silencing. In two independent experiments performed in triplicate each, TCID₅₀ yields were reduced by 62.1±21.2% upon GPx8 silencing. Of note, intracellular HCV RNA levels were not affected significantly in cells silenced for GPx8 (data not shown), suggesting that GPx8 does not affect HCV entry and RNA replication.

To confirm the latter notion, Huh-7.5 cells overexpressing GPx8 or treated with GPx8 siRNAs were transfected with subgenomic HCV replicons or infected with HCVpp, respectively. As shown in Figure 4C, the efficiency of HCV RNA replication was equal in Huh-7.5 cells overexpressing GPx8 as compared to cells expressing GFP as a control. In addition, silencing of GPx8 did not affect HCV RNA replication (Fig. 4D). Moreover, no significant difference in the efficiency of HCVpp entry into cells overexpressing GPx8 as compared to parental Huh-7.5 cells or cells treated with GPx8 siRNAs as compared to the nonrelevant control siRNA was observed (Fig. 4E).

These results indicated that GPx8 was found to facilitate HCV particle production but not cell entry or RNA replication. As total, i.e. intra- and extracellular infectious virus yields increased or decreased upon GPx8 overexpression vs. silencing, respectively (Fig. 4A and 4B), GPx8 is likely involved in HCV assembly, although an additional effect on particle release cannot be excluded.

Catalytically active site of GPx8 plays an important role in HCV particle production. To analyze the roles of cleavage of GPx8 by HCV NS3-4A protease, we employed retroviruses expressing the GFP as a control, GPx8, uncleavable GPx8 (C11A), N-terminally truncated GPx8 (S12), and moreover catalytically inactive GPx8 (C79T) which was replaced in GPx8 position 79 by Thr followed by infection with Jc1 HCVcc. As shown in Figure 5A, cells overexpressing not only GPx8, as well as uncleavable GPx8 (C11A) and N-terminally truncated GPx8 (S12) produced more infectious virus as compared to cells expressing GFP as a control. On the other hand cells overexpressing catalytically inactive GPx8 (C79T) produced virus particle equivalent to GFP control. As shown in Fig. 5B, the efficiency of HCV RNA replication was similar in Huh-7.5 cells overexpressing different variants of GPx8 as compared to cells expressing GFP as a control.

FIG. 5. The catalytically active site of GPx8 plays a role in HCV particle production. (A) Huh-7.5 cells were transiently transduced with retroviruses (multiplicity of infection [MOI] = 10) expressing GFP, GPx8, uncleavable GPx8 (C11A), N-terminally truncated GPx8 (S12), and catalytically inactive GPx8 (C79T), followed 1 d later by Jc1 HCVcc infection (MOI = 0.5). Extra- and intracellular infectivity were determined 3 d post-HCVcc infection by TCID₅₀ titration. Total infectivity represents the sum of extra- and intracellular infectivity. (B) Lysates were separated by 12% SDS-PAGE, followed by immunoblot using monoclonal antibody (mAb) C7-50 against HCV core, polyclonal antibody IN103 against GPx8, and mAb AC-15 against β -actin. A total of 10 μ g protein per lane was loaded for the lysates. Arrowheads denote the position of full-length (FL) and cleaved (Cl.) GPx8.

These results indicated that catalytically active site of GPx8 plays a role in virus particle production, however the function of cleavage of GPx8 by NS3-4A remain an open question.

DISCUSSION

SILAC coupled with molecular weight-based protein separation and MS identified the membrane-associated peroxidase GPx8 as a novel cellular substrate of the NS3-4A protease. Cleavage by NS3-4A occurs at Cys 11, removing the cytosolic tip of GPx8. It was observed in models of HCV infection involving different viral genotypes as well as in liver biopsies from patients with chronic hepatitis C. Furthermore, overexpression and RNA silencing studies revealed that GPx8 is involved in viral particle production but not in HCV entry or RNA replication.

A non-hepatic cell line allowing the tightly regulated expression of the NS3-4A complex was used in this study. Alternative approaches, such as the use of naïve vs. replicon-harboring or HCVcc-infected Huh-7 or Huh-7.5 cells appeared less suitable for our purpose, as a vast number of proteins are likely to be up- or downregulated in these settings, rendering the identification of *bona fide* NS3-4A protease substrates more difficult. Moreover, transfection or retroviral transduction of Huh-7 or other liver-derived cell lines may introduce clonal artefacts, which may complicate analyses. Based on these considerations, we have opted for the use of the well-characterized and tightly regulated U-2 OS-derived cell line UNS3-4A-24 for screening and to include Huh-7.5 cells transfected with subgenomic HCV replicons or infected with HCVcc as well as liver biopsies from patients with chronic hepatitis C in the subsequent validation.

A crucial parameter of our "slice-SILAC" approach was the resolution of molecular weight-based separation, which is determined by the number of SDS-PAGE slices taken. Indeed, the high number of gel slices taken in this study allowed for the detection of molecular weight shifts as small as 2 kDa, as it was the case for GPx8, which would have been missed with a less fine fractionation.

Similar strategies have been described recently to identify caspase substrates³⁰ or for the analysis of protein isoforms and their turnover.³¹ The coupling of SILAC with SDS-PAGE separation applied in this study is in fact not specific for proteolytic cleavage events but can detect any change in gel electrophoretic mobility. Apart from proteolysis, such shifts can also result from changes in post-translational modifications (e.g., ubiquitination or glycosylation) or a switch between splice variants of the same protein, possibly explaining why some of the candidates identified in our study, such as Rab34 and cytochrome b5, could not be confirmed as proteolytic substrates of the NS3-4A (K.M., J.G., H.T.L.T., M.Q. and D.M., unpublished data).

As the other cellular substrates of the NS3-4A protease identified thus far, i.e. MAVS, TRIF, TC-PTP and DDB1 (cf. Introduction section and ref. 3), GPx8 displays a non-canonical NS3-

4A *trans*-cleavage site. Indeed, GPx8 carries an Ala in the P6 position which in the HCV polyprotein is occupied by an acidic residue (Asp or Glu). We believe that substrate specificity may also be determined by the topology of the NS3-4A protease active site, which is defined by NS3 N-terminal amphipathic helix α_0 , the N-terminal transmembrane segment of NS4A, and NS3 loop 38-40, resulting in tripod-like, strict positioning of the protease active site on the membrane.⁹ Indeed, as illustrated in Figure 2C, the GPx8 cleavage site fits perfectly with our previous prediction.⁹ These observations underpin the use of a cellular system to search for novel substrates of the NS3-4A protease.

GPx8 belongs to the glutathione peroxidase family but it has recently been shown to have protein disulfide isomerase (PDI) rather than glutathione peroxidase activity.²⁷ It interacts with the sulfhydryl oxidase Ero1 α (ER oxidoreductin-1 α) in the ER lumen and facilitates the use of peroxide produced by Ero1 α during disulfide bond formation.²⁷

Here, we show that the catalytically active site of GPx8 facilitates HCV particle production but does not impact on HCV entry or RNA replication. Future studies will be aimed at determining whether GPx8 acts through a direct mechanism, e.g. by facilitating HCV envelope glycoprotein disulfide bond formation and folding in the ER lumen, or through indirect mechanism(s), e.g. by limiting HCV-induced ER stress and the unfolded protein response. In addition, future studies shall investigate whether GPx8 cleavage by the NS3-4A protease is beneficial to the virus, e.g. by redirecting GPx8 to viral assembly sites, or whether cleavage reduces GPx8 function in an attempt of the virus to limit particle production as opposed to polyprotein translation and RNA replication. In this study we used overexpression setting to analyze the significance of GPx8 cleavage, yet we could not get obvious answer to why HCV NS3-4A needs to cleave the cytosolic part of GPx8. Clearly, more physiological cell-based methods to assess the function of full-length and truncated GPx8 will have to be developed for this purpose. Such methods should also provide insights into the role of the cytoplasmic tip and the transmembrane segment which are unique to GPx8 as opposed to other GPx family members.

In conclusion, using quantitative proteomics we identified the membrane-associated peroxidase GPx8 as a cellular substrate of the HCV NS3-4A protease. Identification of such novel targets should enhance our understanding of the life cycle as well as pathogenesis of HCV and may reveal new angles for therapeutic intervention in the future. In addition, the methodology described in this study may be applied to the discovery of host targets of other viral proteases, e.g. those of related *Flaviviridae* family members, the hepatitis A^{32,33} and E viruses as well as HIV and other medically important viruses.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge Jachen Barblan, Rosa Castillo, Audrey Kennel and Alexandra Potts for expert technical assistance, Lloyd Ruddock for helpful discussions and critical reading of the manuscript, Pantxika Bellecave for contributions in the early phase of this project, as well as Ralf Bartenschlager, Angela Ciuffi, Charles M. Rice and Didier Trono for reagents.

REFERENCES

1. Nature Outlook: Hepatitis C. *Nature* 2011;474:S1-S21.
2. Moradpour D, Penin F, Rice CM. Replication of hepatitis C virus. *Nat Rev Microbiol* 2007;5:453-463.
3. Morikawa K, Lange CM, Gouttenoire J, Meylan E, Brass V, Penin F, Moradpour D. Nonstructural protein 3-4A: the Swiss army knife of hepatitis C virus. *J Viral Hepat* 2011;18:305-315.
4. Swiss Association for the Study of the Liver. Treatment of chronic hepatitis C genotype 1 with triple therapy comprising telaprevir or boceprevir. *Swiss Med Wkly* 2012;142:w13516.
5. Meylan E, Curran J, Hofmann K, Moradpour D, Binder M, Bartenschlager R, Tschopp J. Cardif is an adaptor protein in the RIG-I antiviral pathway and is targeted by hepatitis C virus. *Nature* 2005;437:1167-1172.
6. Li K, Foy E, Ferreon JC, Nakamura M, Ferreon AC, Ikeda M, Ray SC, et al. Immune evasion by hepatitis C virus NS3/4A protease-mediated cleavage of the Toll-like receptor 3 adaptor protein TRIF. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2005;102:2992-2997.
7. Brenndörfer ED, Karthe J, Frelin L, Cebula P, Erhardt A, Schulte am Esch J, Hengel H, et al. Nonstructural 3/4A protease of hepatitis C virus activates epithelial growth factor-induced signal transduction by cleavage of the T-cell protein tyrosine phosphatase. *Hepatology* 2009;49:1810-1820.
8. Kang X, Chen X, He Y, Guo D, Guo L, Zhong J, Shu HB. DDB1 is a cellular substrate of NS3/4A protease and required for hepatitis C virus replication. *Virology* 2013, in press.
9. Brass V, Berke JM, Montserret R, Blum HE, Penin F, Moradpour D. Structural determinants for membrane association and dynamic organization of the hepatitis C virus NS3-4A complex. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2008;105:14545-14550.
10. Mann M. Functional and quantitative proteomics using SILAC. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol* 2006;7:952-958.
11. Grakoui A, Wychowski C, Lin C, Feinstone SM, Rice CM. Expression and identification of hepatitis C virus polyprotein cleavage products. *J Virol* 1993;67:1385-1395.
12. Kolykhalov AA, Agapov EV, Blight KJ, Mihalik K, Feinstone SM, Rice CM. Transmission of hepatitis C by intrahepatic inoculation with transcribed RNA. *Science* 1997;277:570-574.

13. Wölk B, Sansonno D, Kräusslich H-G, Dammacco F, Rice CM, Blum HE, Moradpour D. Subcellular localization, stability and *trans*-cleavage competence of the hepatitis C virus NS3-NS4A complex expressed in tetracycline-regulated cell lines. *J Virol* 2000;74:2293-2304.
14. Schmidt-Mende J, Bieck E, Hügler T, Penin F, Rice CM, Blum HE, Moradpour D. Determinants for membrane association of the hepatitis C virus RNA-dependent RNA polymerase. *J Biol Chem* 2001;276:44052-44063.
15. Blight KJ, McKeating JA, Rice CM. Highly permissive cell lines for subgenomic and genomic hepatitis C virus RNA replication. *J Virol* 2002;76:13001-13014.
16. Wilm M, Shevchenko A, Houthaeve T, Breit S, Schweigerer L, Fotsis T, Mann M. Femtomole sequencing of proteins from polyacrylamide gels by nano-electrospray mass spectrometry. *Nature* 1996;379:466-469.
17. Cox J, Mann M. MaxQuant enables high peptide identification rates, individualized p.p.b.-range mass accuracies and proteome-wide protein quantification. *Nat Biotechnol* 2008;26:1367-1372.
18. Schaller T, Appel N, Koutsoudakis G, Kallis S, Lohmann V, Pietschmann T, Bartenschlager R. Analysis of hepatitis C virus superinfection exclusion by using novel fluorochrome gene-tagged viral genomes. *J Virol* 2007;81:4591-4603.
19. Pietschmann T, Kaul A, Koutsoudakis G, Shavinskaya A, Kallis S, Steinmann E, Abid K, et al. Construction and characterization of infectious intragenotypic and intergenotypic hepatitis C virus chimeras. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2006;103:7408-7413.
20. Moradpour D, Evans MJ, Gosert R, Yuan ZH, Blum HE, Goff SP, Lindenbach BD, et al. Insertion of green fluorescent protein into nonstructural protein 5A allows direct visualization of functional hepatitis C virus replication complexes. *J Virol* 2004;78:7400-7409.
21. Bellecave P, Gouttenoire J, Gajer M, Brass V, Koutsoudakis G, Blum HE, Bartenschlager R, et al. Hepatitis B and C virus coinfection: A novel model system reveals the absence of direct viral interference. *Hepatology* 2009;50:46-55.
22. Lindenbach BD, Evans MJ, Syder AJ, Wölk B, Tellinghuisen TL, Liu CC, Maruyama T, et al. Complete replication of hepatitis C virus in cell culture. *Science* 2005;309:623-626.
23. Maillard PV, Reynard S, Serhan F, Turelli P, Trono D. Interfering residues narrow the spectrum of MLV restriction by human TRIM5 α . *PLoS Pathog* 2007;3:e200.

24. Bartosch B, Dubuisson J, Cosset FL. Infectious hepatitis C virus pseudo-particles containing functional E1-E2 envelope protein complexes. *J Exp Med* 2003;197:633-642.
25. Combet C, Blanchet C, Geourjon C, Deléage G. NPS@: network protein sequence analysis. *Trends Biochem Sci* 2000;25:147-150.
26. Guex N, Peitsch MC. SWISS-MODEL and the Swiss-PdbViewer: an environment for comparative protein modeling. *Electrophoresis* 1997;18:2714-2723.
27. Nguyen VD, Saaranen MJ, Karala AR, Lappi AK, Wang L, Raykhel IB, Alanen HI, et al. Two endoplasmic reticulum PDI peroxidases increase the efficiency of the use of peroxide during disulfide bond formation. *J Mol Biol* 2011;406:503-515.
28. Page RC, Clark JG, Misra S. Structure of filamin A immunoglobulin-like repeat 10 from *Homo sapiens*. *Acta Crystallogr Sect F Struct Biol Cryst Commun* 2011;67:871-876.
29. Shinoda T, Ogawa H, Cornelius F, Toyoshima C. Crystal structure of the sodium-potassium pump at 2.4 Å resolution. *Nature* 2009;459:446-450.
30. Pham VC, Pitti R, Anania VG, Bakalarski CE, Bustos D, Jhunjunwala S, Phung QT, et al. Complementary proteomic tools for the dissection of apoptotic proteolysis events. *J Proteome Res* 2012;11:2947-2954.
31. Ahmad Y, Boisvert FM, Lundberg E, Uhlen M, Lamond AI. Systematic analysis of protein pools, isoforms, and modifications affecting turnover and subcellular localization. *Mol Cell Proteomics* 2012;11:M111 013680.
32. Qu L, Feng Z, Yamane D, Liang Y, Lanford RE, Li K, Lemon SM. Disruption of TLR3 signaling due to cleavage of TRIF by the hepatitis A virus protease-polymerase processing intermediate, 3CD. *PLoS Pathog* 2011;7:e1002169.
33. Yang Y, Liang Y, Qu L, Chen Z, Yi M, Li K, Lemon SM. Disruption of innate immunity due to mitochondrial targeting of a picornaviral protease precursor. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2007;104:7253-7258.
34. Humphrey W, Dalke A, Schulten K. VMD: visual molecular dynamics. *J Mol Graph* 1996;14:33-8, 27-8.